

Cancer, Hormones & Blood Pharmacology

ANTICOAGULANTS, BLOOD CLOTTING DRUGS & REVERSAL AGENTS

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Primary Hemostasis (Platelet function test)

Secondary Hemostasis (aPTT, PT, TT)

Anticoagulant agents

Prevent clot formation

- Heparin and its derivatives
- Warfarin
- Direct oral anticoagulants (DOACs)

Resolve existing clot

- Fibrinolytic agents

Prevent excessive bleeding

- Reversal agents

Hemostasis

= reversal agent

Heparin

(Xa/thrombin inhibitor)

MOA: Negatively charged polysaccharide that forms a complex with endogenous antithrombin III (ATIII)

- Heparin-ATIII complex: Irreversibly inactivates thrombin and factor Xa
- Enoxaparin (LMWH): greater bioavailability and longer duration of action but have less of an effect on thrombin inhibition

Therapeutics: Acute MI, venous thromboembolism prevention, deep vein thrombosis and pulmonary embolism treatment

- Anticoagulant effect monitored by PTT

Adverse Effects: Increased incidence of bleeding.

- A small number of patients may develop thrombocytopenia (HIT)

Heparin and its Derivatives

UFH > LMWH > Fondaparinux

Unfractionated heparin (MW: 15 kDa)

- Binds antithrombin
- Indirectly inhibits Factor Xa and thrombin activity

Enoxaparin

- Low Molecular Weight Heparin (Ave. MW 4.5 kDa)
- Binds antithrombin
- More effective at indirect inhibition of Factor Xa than thrombin (length dependent)

Fondaparinux

- Pentasaccharide that binds antithrombin
- Indirectly inhibits Factor Xa only, no thrombin inhibition

Protamine Sulfate

(heparin reversal agent)

MOA: Highly cationic peptide that binds to heparin

- Blocks interaction of heparin with antithrombin
- Stable ionic complex formed prevents inactivation of thrombin and Factor Xa

Pharmacokinetics:

- Short half-life
- Repeated doses may be required

Therapeutics: Reverse significant bleeding by heparin

Warfarin (VKORC1 inhibitor)

MOA: VKORC1 inhibitor

- Inhibits the recycling of vitamin K in the liver
- ↓ Anticoag proteins (C,S)
 - Short $t_{1/2}$ so occurs 1st
 - Increase risk of clot formation
- ↓ Clotting factors (FII, FVII, FIX, X)
 - Longer $t_{1/2}$ so occurs later
 - Inhibits clot formation

Therapeutics: Thromboembolism, PE, myocardial infarction, atrial fibrillation

- Dosing – highly variable among individuals.
- Monitor anticoagulation effects by PT/INR
- Amount of vitamin K in diet can impact PT/INR
- Initial bridging therapy with heparin/LMWH

Adverse Effects: Bleeding, skin necrosis

- Major cause of emergency hospitalization
- Narrow therapeutic window – “can cause major or fatal bleeding”

Warfarin (VKORC1 inhibitor)

Reversal Agents:

- **4-factor prothrombin complex concentrate (rapid reversal)**
 - Replacement therapy
 - Contains factors II, VII, IX, X
- **Fresh frozen plasma (if PCC unavailable)**
 - Contains all coagulation factors
 - Deficiency in multiple factors documented
- **Vitamin K (longer-term)**
 - Promotes synthesis of vitamin K dependent clotting factors

Warfarin (VKORC1 inhibitor)

Pharmacokinetics:

- Dosing highly variable among patients
 - Polymorphisms in VKORC1 and CYP2C9
- Warfarin metabolized mainly by CYP2C9
 - Clearance of warfarin is almost entirely dependent on metabolism.
- Drug-drug interactions with warfarin are important to consider due to the narrow therapeutic index
- Narrow therapeutic index

Direct Oral Anticoagulants (DOACs)

Rivaroxaban

- Binds to and directly inhibits Xa
- Reversal: Andexanet alfa
 - Recombinant factor Xa decoy (lacks membrane-binding domain)

Dabigatran

- Binds to and directly inhibits IIa/thrombin
- Reversal: Idarucizumab
 - Fc antibody fragment against dabigatran

Therapeutics:

- Deep vein thrombosis
- Pulmonary embolism
- PT/INR/aPTT monitoring not recommended/necessary

Adverse Effect:

- Bleeding, GI stress

Alteplase (thrombolytic)

MOA: Recombinant tissue plasminogen activator (tPA)

- Binds to fibrin in thrombus
- Converts plasminogen to plasmin
- Plasmin initiates local fibrinolysis

Therapeutics: Pulmonary embolism with hypotension, proximal DVT, MI, stroke

Adverse Effects:

- Bleeding, GI and cerebral hemorrhaging

ε-Aminocaproic acid / TXA (anti-fibrinolytics)

MOA: Lysine analogs

- Binds lysine binding site on plasminogen
- Prevents plasmin formation

Therapeutics: Various forms of bleeding

- Tranexamic acid (3x more potent)

Adverse Effect: Thrombosis

HEMOPHILIA

BLOOD MEDIFAMILY

Recombinant clotting factors (replacement)

- **Recombinant FVIII: Replacement for hemophilia A**
- **Recombinant FIX: Replacement for hemophilia B**
- **Humate-P: VWF/FVIII concentrate derived from human plasma**
 - Replacement for VWD and hemophilia A
- **Recombinant FVIIa: Treatment for autoimmune hemophilia**
 - Activates the extrinsic pathway as a rescue for the inhibited intrinsic pathway

Desmopressin (DDAVP) (vasopressin analog)

MOA: Vasopressin type 2 receptor agonist

- Water reabsorption in the medullary collecting duct
- Stimulates endothelial release of von Willebrand factor and factor VIII
- **Therapeutics:** Type 1 von Willebrand Disease (ineffective for Type 2 and 3 vWD)
- Diabetes insipidus (low ADH secretion)

Adverse Effects: Hyponatremia, body fluid retention

Emicizumab

(anti-FIXa/FX bispecific antibody)

MOA: anti-FIXa/FX bispecific antibody

- Mimics function of activated FVIII
- Brings together FIXa and FX to activate FX, (acts as a bypassing agent)
- **Therapeutics:** Hemophilia A ± factor VIII inhibitors (prophylaxis)

Adverse Effects: Injection-site reaction, headache, joint pain, thrombotic microangiopathy (TMA)

Hemostasis

= reversal agent

Coagulation Drug Mnemonics

Anticoag drugs:

Heparin	Xa & thrombin antagonist
Enoxaparin	Xa antagonist
Fondaparinux	Xa antagonist
Rivaroxiban	Xa direct antagonist
Dabigatran	Thrombin direct antagonist
Warfarin	VKORC1 antagonist

Thrombosis regulation drugs:

Alteplase	Converts plasminogen → plasmin
ε-aminocaproic acid	Plasminogen inhibitor
Tranexamic acid	Plasminogen inhibitor

Clotting factor drugs:

rFVIII	FVIII
rFIX	FVIX
Humate-P	VWF + FVIII
Desmopressin	V2 receptor agonist
Emicizumab	anti-FIXa/FX bispecific antibody

Heparin

He **throbs** for a **10** (**thrombin/Xa**)

Enoxaparin

Xa (the target is in the name)

Warfarin

The **South Carolina 7-day war** of **1092**

Anticoag reversal drugs:

4-factor PCC.	Factors II, VII, IX, X
FFP	Plasma containing clotting factors
Vit K	Vitamin K
Protamine sulfate	Heparin inhibitor
Idarucizumab	anti-Dabigatran antibody
Andexanet alfa	Decoy Xa (rivaroxaban inhibitor)

Andexanet alfa

Xa (the target is in the name)

the twilight saga

breaking elots

the twilight saga

breaking clots

Mnemonic	Meaning
<p>The werewolves have dammed the river which is causing the town and crops to die.</p>	<p>A clot obstructing an artery can cause ischemia and tissue death.</p>
<p>Bella attacks the dam with hairpins, which the werewolves block with Proh Solvite shields</p>	<p>Heparin is an anticoagulant that can be reversed with protamine sulfate.</p>
<p>Edward HITs fastballs at the dam, which only cause the Platelet Medimon to fall off.</p>	<p>An adverse effect of heparin treatment is heparin-induced thrombocytopenia (HIT) causing a decrease in platelet levels.</p>
<p>Edward calls in an "X" truck to let the river rock the dam, but is blocked by a Dexa Net from Jacob the alpha wolf.</p>	<p>Rivaroxaban is a direct factor Xa inhibitor which can be reversed with Andexanet alpha.</p>
<p>Edward and Bella declare war on the werewolves and use a K-bomb received from the Volturi (numbered robes)</p>	<p>Warfarin inhibits vitamin K metabolism, leading to decrease in factors II, VII, IX, and X.</p>
<p>The K-bomb causes the town to be flooded and Bella to get necrotic burns.</p>	<p>Warfarin adverse effects included increased risk of bleeding and warfarin-induced skin necrosis.</p>
<p>Edward and Bella are arrested by CYP robots and charged with war CrYmes for flooding the town.</p>	<p>CYP2C9 mutations can cause increased levels of warfarin leading to increased risk of bleeding.</p>

the twilight saga breaking clots

Bella used her hairpins (heparin) to try and break the dam (clot), but the werewolves were able to stop this attack.

What did they use to block the hairpin attack and what does it represent?

Proh Solvite Shields : Protein Sulfate

Protein sulfate is the reversal agent for heparin. It is a large positively charged molecule that binds to and neutralizes the highly negatively charged heparin molecules.

the twilight saga breaking elots

Directly after the hairpin attack, Edward decided to HIT fastballs at the dam, but this only caused the loss of the Platelet Medimon.

Other than increase bleeding risk, what is the adverse effect of heparin?

Heparin-induced thrombocytopenia (HIT)

Heparin can bind to PF4. Autoantibodies to this complex can bind to heparin-PF4 and cause platelet to become activated. This leads to thrombocytopenia, which typically occurs 5-10 days after initiation of heparin.

the twilight saga breaking clots

A Dexa Net was used by Jacob (the alpha wolf) to block one of the attempts by Edward and Bella to destroy the dam.

What type of treatment does
Andexanet alpha reverse?

Rivaroxaban (River rocks the dam)
*Direct factor Xa inhibitors (rivaroxaban) can be reversed
with Andexanet alpha which acts like a decoy factor Xa
to bind and inhibit rivaroxaban.*

the twilight saga breaking clots

Eventually Edward and Bella declare war on the werewolves, and use a K-bomb to explode the dam.

How does warfarin inhibit clotting?

***Inhibit vitamin K metabolism (VKORC1) /
Decrease levels of FII, VII, IX, X***

Warfarin inhibits the metabolism of vitamin K in the liver by inhibiting VKORC1. This prevents the liver from producing the clotting factors II, VII, IX, and X.

the twilight saga

breaking elots

The K-bomb explosion caused Bella to get a necrotic burn.

Other than increase bleeding risk, what is the adverse effect of warfarin?

Warfarin-induced skin necrosis

Warfarin treatment first leads to decreased levels of protein C/S which can lead to a hypercoagulable state. This can lead to microvascular thromobis → ischemia → and necrosis.

the twilight saga breaking elots

Unfortunately, the K-bomb worked too good, and the town flooded due to the destruction of the dam. Edward and Bella were then arrested by CYP robots for their war crimes.

How do CYP mutations affect warfarin treatment?

CYP2C9 mutations require lower dosing

Warfarin is metabolized mainly by CYP2C9, so inactivating mutations in this CYP can cause increase warfarin levels which can lead to increased risk of bleeding.

Questions?

High-yield slides can be viewed at www.blandpharm.com

Hemostasis

⌚ = reversal agent

Worksheets & Practice ?'s

(practice makes permanent)

Interactive worksheets and practice questions at www.blandpharm.com

Medimon mnemonics can be viewed at www.medimon.games

PHARMACOLOGY STEP 1 CK

Hemostasis

Drug	Target			Side Effects
Fondaparinux		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
Warfarin		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
Rivaroxaban		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
Heparin		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
PCC		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
Vitamin K		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
ϵ -Aminocaproic acid		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
Protamine Sulfate		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
Enoxaparin		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
Humate-P		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
Idarucizumab		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
FFP		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
Alteplase		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
Eminicizumab		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
FVIIa		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
Dabigatran		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
FIX		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
FVIII		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	
Andexanet alfa		<input type="checkbox"/> Agonist	<input type="checkbox"/> Antagonist	

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